

The Heckscher-Ohlin model's applicability in Colombia

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October 2024

1. Introduction

Colombia, a country known for its rich endowment of natural resources —such as oil, minerals, and extensive agricultural land— has developed a trade pattern that reflects its economic structure. These natural resources play a central role in shaping both Colombia's domestic production and its interactions in the global marketplace. To export such goods, Colombia relies on its factors of production, which the Heckscher-Ohlin (H-O) model studies, providing a theoretical framework which seeks to explain how a country's trade patterns are influenced by its relative abundance or scarcity of factors of production. Bearing this in mind, this essay will critically explore the extent to which the H-O model can explain Colombia's trade patterns and economic behavior.

2. The Heckscher-Ohlin Model

The Heckscher-Ohlin (H-O) model is a pillar of international trade theory, explaining how differences in countries' factor endowments determine their comparative advantage and trade patterns. According to this model, trade flows are driven by the relative abundance of factors — labor and capital— in different countries. The fundamental principle is that countries with an abundant factor of production will specialize in the production and export of goods that are factor intensive, while countries with factor scarcity will import such goods. It delegates the pricing of goods to the international trade market, which, in turn, will dictate production levels.

To predict trade patterns, the H-O model makes a series of assumptions, such as the existence of only two factors— labor and capital (L and K) —, fixed factor quantities, and same level of technology between countries, which highly differs from the real world.

3. Colombia's factor endowment

To assess the predictions of the Heckscher-Ohlin model, it is essential to evaluate the availability of production factors in Colombia. Firstly, capital (K), which encompasses machinery, infrastructure, technology, and other assets contributing to production. In Colombia, K is evaluated through the gross Fixed Capital Formation (FKF), which measures investment in capital goods. It represented 18.5% of Colombia's GDP in 2022, a low level compared to other emerging economies. This limits the country's ability to compete in global markets with higher value-added and more complex products.

As to labor (L), the size of Colombia's economically active population (EAP), was close to 25 million in 2023. However, 58% of the working population belongs to the informal labor scope (García et al., 2024). Lack of investment in education and technology has prevented diversification into labor-intensive sectors, such as manufacturing, which accounted for only 12% of exports in 2023. Additionally, Colombia's low relative minimum wage makes it an attractive country for production, having the third lowest minimum wage in South America, amounting to \$249 USD in 2023, just behind Brazil and Peru. (Visual Capitalist, 2023)

Furthermore, labor has a greater impact on GDP than Capital in Colombia. According to the Cobb-Douglas function for Colombia, established by Bodden & Orjuela (2018), a 1% increase in EAP raises GDP by 0.62%. By contrast, A 1% increase in FKF raises GDP by 0.28%. Thereupon, increased productivity of labor leads to a direct, significant boost in economic output.

Based on such data, Colombia is considered a labor abundant country relative to capital. This leads to the H-O model predicting that Colombia, should specialize in and export labor-intensive goods, while importing capital intensive goods.

4. Colombia's real-life Trade patterns

Colombia's top 5 exported goods in 2024 consisted of Petroleum oils (22,8% of the exported products), bituminous coal (16,4%), gold (8,7%), coffee (6,3%) and refined oil (5,6%). United States, Panama, China, Brazil, India, and South Korea were the main export destinations. These six countries accounted for 54.1% of Colombia's total sales. (Ministerio de Comercio, Industria y Turismo, 2024)

Table 1. Participation (%) of exported products in the Colombian economy as of July 2024. (Ministerio de Comercio, Industria y Turismo, 2024)

Fuente: DANE-DIAN. Cálculos OEE – MINCIT.

Bearing this in mind, despite the H-O model predictions regarding labor intensive goods, Colombia tends to export capital intensive goods in the mining and crude sectors. The only labor dependent good is coffee; however, its traded quantity is low compared to other goods.

The fact that Colombia depends so much on its natural resources for its exports also means that it is more exposed to fluctuations in global commodity prices, which generates economic instability. A study shows for every dollar the price of oil drops, Colombia loses \$16 million USD. (Medina, 2024)

On the other hand, due to capital scarcity, the country imported capital-intensive goods, such as refined oil, transmission apparatuses for radiotelephony, aircraft pieces, medicaments and machinery with high added value in 2024.

Table 2. Main imported products by Colombia in millions of dollars as of July 2024. (Ministerio de Comercio, Industria y Turismo, 2024)

Partida	Descripción	Julio		Variación %
		2023	2024	2024/2023
2710	Petróleo refinado	338,6	405,7	19,8
8703	Automóviles de turismo	222,3	329,6	48,3
8517	Teléfonos	181,2	226,6	25,0
3004	Medicamentos dosificados	197,6	207,6	5,1
8802	Demás aeronaves	293,6	127,9	-56,4
8471	Máquinas para procesamiento de	87,1	124,6	43,0
3002	Sangre para usos terapéuticos	90,9	121,7	34,0
8502	Grupos electrógenos	9,3	115,1	1.135,1
1005	Maíz	147,2	80,4	-45,4
8704	Vehículos para mercancías	70,8	78,8	11,3
8429	Topadoras frontales	25,4	78,6	209,3
9801	Motocicletas	47,7	63,7	33,6
4011	Neumáticos nuevos	44,5	55,4	24,3
3808	Insecticidas	39,0	53,6	37,4
9018	Instrumentos para medicina	46,8	52,4	12,1
Subtotal		1.842	2.122	15,2
Participación %		37,2%	38,0%	
Importaciones totales		4.945	5.581	12,9

Fuente: DANE-DIAN

This trade pattern is in line with the Heckscher-Ohlin model, which predicts that countries import goods that require intensive use of factors in which they are less abundant.

5. Conclusion

Colombia's economic landscape reveals a reliance on labor as its primary factor of production. This dependency arises from low levels of Fixed Capital Formation and a relatively low minimum wage, which keep labor costs accessible and underscore the country's dependence on its Economically Active Population for economic growth. Notably, a 1% increase in EAP results in a more substantial GDP rise than an equivalent increase in capital investment. However, despite this emphasis on labor, Colombia's economy is shaped by capital-intensive sectors, particularly in oil and mining, contrary to the H-O model's predictions.

The H-O model's assumptions may explain the dissonance between real life and theoretical scenarios, given the fact that it overlooks key trade influences like commodity prices, tariffs, and trade agreements, while assuming identical tastes and preferences; hence falling short when explaining the export dynamics dominated by primary, capital-intensive goods.

Additionally, this concentration of capital in primary industries highlights the country's vulnerability to international price fluctuations and external demand shifts. Therefore, diversifying the Colombian economy through capital accumulation and value-added industries will be essential for reducing vulnerability and achieving sustainable growth. In pursuing industrialization and diversification, Colombia has the opportunity to capitalize on advances in technology and evolving global consumption patterns, aiming to build a resilient economy that balances resource exploitation with the transformation of raw materials and innovation.

References & Bibliography:

Bodden, A. & Orjuela, E. (July, 2018) Función De Producción Cobb- Douglas Aplicada Al Producto Interno Bruto Colombiano. Universidad Piloto de Colombia.

<https://repository.unipiloto.edu.co/bitstream/handle/20.500.12277/4805/00005017.pdf?sequence=1>

García, J. B., Castrillón, C., Rendón, A. H., Franco, H., & Vargas, C. (2024). Formality and informality in an emerging economy: The case of colombia. *Cuadernos de economía (Santafé de Bogotá)*, 43(91), 345-373.

Medina, M. (August 6, 2024) *Por cada dólar que baja el precio del petróleo, Colombia deja de ganar US\$16 millones* La República. Retrieved from <https://www.larepublica.co/especiales/lunes-negro-2024/por-cada-dolar-que-baja-el-precio-del-petroleo-colombia-deja-de-ganar-us-16-millones-3923765>

Ministerio de Comercio, Industria y Turismo (July, 2024) Exportaciones de Colombia, a julio del 2024 Retrieved from <https://www.mincit.gov.co/estudios-economicos/estadisticas-e-informes/informes-de-exportacion>

Ministerio de Comercio, Industria y Turismo (July, 2024) Importaciones y balanza comercial, julio de 2024 Retrieved from <https://www.mincit.gov.co/getattachment/estudios-economicos/estadisticas-e-informes/informes-de-importaciones-colombianas-y-balanza-co/2024/julio/oee-ma-informe-de-importaciones-y-balanza-comercial-julio-2024.pdf.aspx>

World Bank (2022) Colombia Trade Retrieved from <https://wits.worldbank.org/CountrySnapshot/en/COL/textview>

Visual Capitalist (March 2023) Mapped: Minimum Wage Around the World. Retrieved from
<https://www.visualcapitalist.com/minimum-wage-around-the-world/>